

How to Improve Flooding-related Emergency Management for Rural Communities in Southern Illinois

Q1: As a service provider or supporting group member, I feel that timely decision making support is most needed i...

Answers

Count

Percentage

Preparedness (planning)	14	77.78%
Response	16	88.89%
Mitigation	5	27.78%
Recovery	11	61.11%

Answered: 18 Skipped: 0

Q2: As a service provider or supporting group member, I feel the following items are highly important to improve e...

Answers

Count

Percentage

Answers	Count	Percentage
More investment into basic infrastructures like roads	7	38.89%
Interorganizational networks to exchange information and coordinate resources	8	44.44%
Better communication between the service providers/supporting groups and the communities in need	12	66.67%
More education efforts to inform all phase of emergency management	7	38.89%

Answered: 18 Skipped: 0

Q3: The current emergency management system needs more coordination and connection.

Answers	Count	Percentage
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Strongly disagree	0	0%
Disagree	2	11.11%
Neutral	5	27.78%
Agree	7	38.89%
Strongly agree	1	5.56%

Answered: 15 Skipped: 3

Q4: At present, what do rural communities mainly rely on to cope with emergency preparedness and response to t...

Answers	Count	Percentage
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Community leadership	5	27.78%
Neighborhood support	8	44.44%
Family self-support	6	33.33%
Federal and state agencies	10	55.56%
Non-profit organizations	4	22.22%

Answered: 18 Skipped: 0

Q5: The rural communities I know currently make flooding preparedness or evacuation decisions based on the info...

Answers	Count	Percentage
Radio	9	50%
Short message service (SMS) from emergency response agencies	7	38.89%
Phone calls from families or friends	8	44.44%
Internet browsing	4	22.22%
Disaster-dedicated smartphone apps	2	11.11%
Social media	10	55.56%
Local newspaper	3	16.67%

Answered: 17 Skipped: 1

Q6: The rural communities I know seek information or resources to cope with flooding based on the information m...

Answers	Count	Percentage
Write emails	0	0%
Call families or friends	8	44.44%
Call local or state agencies	11	61.11%
Internet browsing	3	16.67%
Use disaster-dedicated smartphone apps	1	5.56%
Use social media	10	55.56%
Other	1	5.56%

Answered: 17 Skipped: 1

Q7: Most households from the rural communities I know have internet connections

Answers **Count** **Percentage**

No but only some	3	16.67%
Yes but with poor connection speed	9	50%
Yes with moderate or high speed	4	22.22%
Not sure	2	11.11%

Answered: 18 Skipped: 0

Q8: Most households from the rural communities I know have cell phones

Percentage **ntage**

Yes	18	100%
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No	0	0%
not sure	0	0%

Answered: 18 Skipped: 0

Q9: Please list the name of the rural communities you may know that are highly vulnerable to flooding.

The word cloud requires at least 20 answers to show.

Response	Count
all along the big muddy river in low lying areas.	1
Cairo, Grand Tower, East Cape, McClure	1
Chester IL, Grand Tower	1
East and south sides of the City of Mount Carmel. There are three levee systems in Wabash County. The Mount Carmel levee is the only one that protects a significant number of structures. Most flood prone areas in the county are agricultural fields. In addition, the levees on the Indiana side of the Wabash River are lower than those on the Illinois side; therefore Indiana acts as a "relief valve" for us.	1
Gorham, Rockwood.	1
Harrisburg, Enfield, Gallatin County, White County	1
metropolis	1
new haven carmi	1
The following counties/communities along the Mississippi and Ohio Rivers Alexander - Cairo, Olive Branch Pulaski Gallatin - Shawneetown, Equality Jackson - Grand Tower Randolph - Chester Massac - Bridgeport Mill Shoals	1
	0

Answered: 9 Skipped: 9

Q10: What do you expect from SIU to support emergency management in Southern Illinois?

The word cloud requires at least 20 answers to show.

Count	Count
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Education on developing in low lying areas and updated and better models on 100-500-1000 yr flood plains. education on working with models and state and federal agencies. best to turn areas into natural wet lands and buy out landowners nature preserves	1
for them to actually be present in the community during a flood. Red Cross comes but no one else	1
GIS	1
no opinion	1
Realistic planning that takes into account the levees. The current "flood stage" of the Wabash River is significantly lower than the actual river depth that would threaten the levees.	1
Research and Studies Education and Training - offer EM courses Partnerships Increased Communication Recovery Groups/Committees Community Grants/Funding Opportunities Resource Sharing/Allocation Support Mitigation Strategies - SIU is part of the community culture, effects of disaster are local, mitigation begins locally. Give IEMA Representative a seat on the board to promote collaboration Promote Alternative Housing for displaced flood victims (lot of empty/unused campus buildings that could be used for alternative living)	1
Support for Training and Education related to all Hazards Preparedness.	1
volunteers	1
	0

Answered: 8 Skipped: 10

Please leave your contact information if you would like to receive future updates or discuss how to collaborate with...

The word cloud requires at least 20 answers to show.

Response	Count
The information was hidden on purpose to protect privacy	1
The information was hidden on purpose to protect privacy	1
The information was hidden on purpose to protect privacy	1
The information was hidden on purpose to protect privacy	1
	0

Answered: 4 Skipped: 14